

Physical Properties of Dihalocarbene Modified Rubbers

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ABSTRACT

The physical properties, mainly adhesive properties, of dihalocarbene modified rubbers were studied compared with halogen additional rubbers. Dihalocarbene modified rubbers showed much higher bond strength than halogen additional rubbers, as adhesive for bonding 1.2 polybutadiene or Nylon6 to metal, which could be attributable to the higher polarity of the former. The discussion was focussed on the relation between bond strength, then polarity and chemical and higher order structure in dihalocarbene modified rubbers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Subjects of interface of materials and adhesion are one of the most important factors on the constitution of composite materials. Actually, many studies for obtaining excellent adhesives have been investigated. (1~5)

Generally, the adhesion quality strongly depends on the polarity of polymer used as adhesives, then many efforts have been made on increasing the polarity of polymers.

Modification, in particular halogenation of rubbers is the general method for obtaining polymers of high polarity, then good adhesive. Most halogenated rubbers usually studied are prepared by the addition of halogens to rubbers, which have β -dihalo structures, freely rotating around carbon-carbon (C-C) bonds (A) shown in Fig.1.

Recently, however, we found that rubbers modified by dihalocarbene, which have α -dihalocyclopropane structure (B) shown in Fig.1 have much better adhesive properties than halogen additional rubbers. (6, 7)

The main differences in chemical structures between dihalocarbene modified and halogen additional rubbers are 1) dipole moment 2) mobility of carbon atom linked to halogen atom 3) steric hindrance 4) electron density of carbon atom linked to halogen atom. Naturally, these differences in chemical structures strongly affect to higher order structures and physical properties of halogenated rubbers.

In this study, we like to mainly discuss the bond strength and the polarity of dihalocarbene modified and halogen additional rubbers from the viewpoint of their molecular and higher order structure.

(A) Halogen additional rubbers (B) Dihalocarbene modified rubbers

Fig.1. Chemical structure of halogenated rubbers

2. EXPERIMENT

2-1) Preparation of halogenated rubbers

Dihalocarbene modified rubbers (B) were obtained by the following reaction, the applied phase transfer catalyst method. (8-11)

Halogen additional rubbers (A) were prepared by the addition of halogens to rubbers.

The rubber used is Syndiotactic 1.2 polybutadiene (Japan Synthetic Rubber Co., RB820 (C)) chemical structure of modified rubber was confirmed by IR and NMR method, and the halogen content in modified rubber was determined by combustion method.

2-2) Preparation of test samples

2-2-1) Preparation of peeling test samples

Samples for peeling test as shown in Fig.2 were prepared as follows, firstly metals of a strip type were polished by a emery paper, degreased in tetrachloroethylene and dried in air at room temperature. Then metal specimens were prepared by applying the 15% solution by weight of the halogenated rubber in methylene chloride on the metals. Finally, test samples were obtained by the

melt coating of 1.2 polybutadiene on the metal specimens at 110°C.

Fig 2. Sample for peeling test

2-2-2) preparation of tensile bond test samples

Disk type specimens were used for tensile bond testing, shown in Fig.3. Nylon6 was injected at 230°C to both sides of the metal specimens of a disk type prepared in a similar manner described above. Test samples were prepared after cooling the specimens thus obtained temperature.

Fig 3. Sample for tensile bond test

2-3) Measurements

2-3-1) Measurement of bond strength

180° peeling strength was measured at peeling rate of 50mm/min, and tensile bond strength was measured at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. All bond strength were measured at 20°C using Instron type tensile tester.

2-3-2) Tape test

On metal specimens of strip type prepared in a similar manner described in 2-2-1), the cellophane-tape (Nichiban Co.,) was stucked sufficiently, then was peeled quickly. The degree of adhesion was evaluated by measuring the fraction of the area where adhesives are remained on the peeled surface. That is, we here adopted the method to give five grades to the surface according to the fraction as follows,

1. perfectly remained ($B/A+B=0\%$)
2. considerably remained ($B/A+B=\text{less than } 30\%$)
3. remained ($B/A+B=30\% \sim 70\%$)
4. slightly remained ($B/A+B=\text{more than } 70\%$)
5. nothing ($B/A+B=100\%$)

A---The part adhesives remained
B---The part adhesives not remained

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3-1) Difference of adhesive property between dihalocarbene modified and halogen additional rubbers

As described in introduction, halogenated rubbers have been used as adhesives. The ability of dihalocarbene modified rubbers as adhesives for bonding 1.2 polybutadiene or Nylon6 to metal, compared with halogen additional rubbers, was evaluated. The results of 180° peeling test for adhesives between 1.2 polybutadiene and metal are presented in Table.1. In this test, Aluminium and Iron were used as metal. The peeling strength was 0~4.0kg/cm for halogen (Bromine) additional rubbers as adhesives. On the contrary, the peeling strength was 10.0~16.0kg/cm for dihalocarbene (dibromocarbene) modified rubbers. In this case, the peeling strength was not changed by using commercial primer (Chemlok 205). On the other hand, the specimen which was directly coated to 1.2 polybutadiene without adhesives gave about 3.0kg/cm and the specimen using commercial adhesive by chlorinated rubber (Chemlok 220) showed the peeling strength of 5.1 kg/cm.

Table 1. Peeling strength between 1.2 polybutadiene and metal

No	Adhesives	Metal	
		Iron	Aluminium
1	Dihalocarbene modified rubber (Bromine 38.5 wt%)	10.0	12.0
2	Dihalocarbene modified rubber (Bromine 23.9 wt%)	14.8	15.2
3	Dihalocarbene modified rubber (Bromine 23.9 wt%) & Commercial primer (Chemlok 205)	15.6	14.8
4	Halogen additional rubbers (Bromine 35.6 wt%)	0.8	3.9
5	—	3.4	3.0
6	Commercial adhesive (Chemlok 220)	5.1	5.1

(Unit) Kg/cm

The results of tensile bond test of Nylon6 to metal are presented in Table.2. The tensile bond strength of specimens where halogen additional rubber (brominated) or commercial adhesive using chlorinated rubber (chemolok 220) were used as adhesives, was negligibly small. On the other hand, for the specimen of dihalocarbene modified rubber (Brominated and chlorinated), the tensile bond strength were about 35 kg/cm² and about 9 kg/cm², respectively. These results clearly show dihalocarbene modified rubbers have higher potentiality in adhesion comparing with halogen additional rubbers.

Table 2. Tensile bond strength between Nylon6 and metal

No	Adhesives	Metal	
		Iron	Aluminium
1	Dihalocarbene modified rubber (Bromine 30.0%)	34.5	35.5
2	Dihalocarbene modified rubber (Chlorine 45.1%)	8.9	8.9
3	Halogen additional rubber (Bromine 35.6%)	≈ 0	≈ 0
4	Commercial adhesive (Chemlok 220)	≈ 0	≈ 0
5	—	≈ 0	≈ 0

(Unit) Kg/cm²

For the results mentioned above, we like to discuss the reason why dihalocarbene modified rubbers have higher potentiality of adhesion than halogen additional rubbers in the following section.

3-2) Contact angle and the affinity to metals

In general, contact angle (θ) between surface layer and solvent gives the

information about the polarity of the surface layer, namely lower the contact angle, higher the polarity. The contact angles measured for dihalocarbene modified and halogen additional rubbers (Brominated samples) are shown in Fig.4 as a function of halogen content, where water was used as solvent.

The contact angle of dihalocarbene modified and halogen additional rubbers became lower with increasing halogen content, which show the polarity of both rubbers increase with halogen content. On the same halogen content, however, dihalocarbene modified rubbers showed the lower contact angle than halogen additional rubbers which indicates that the former have higher polarity than the latter. Moreover, the results of chlorinated rubbers in the contact angle were similar to that of Brominated rubbers shown in Fig.4.

For evaluating the affinity of rubber to metal, a tape test was performed, where brominated rubbers were used as halogenated rubbers, and Aluminium and Iron were used as metal. As shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6, dibromocarbene modified rubbers were perfectly remained at the halogen content of more than 23wt%. On the other hand, bromine additional rubbers were not remained even at the halogen content of 60wt%.

In this test, it is more difficult for films on metal to be peeled out in proportion to the increase the affinity to metal.

These results show that the affinity to metal is stronger in dibromocarbene modified rubbers than in bromine additional rubbers, which means that dihalocarbene modified rubbers have the higher polarity than halogen additional rubbers.

It can be assumed, therefore, that the difference in the polarity of both halogenated rubbers must be one of the most important factors for the high potentiality of adhesion of dihalocarbene modified rubbers compared with halogen additional rubbers. Then, we like to consider the difference in the polarity of both rubbers from the view point of their chemical and higher order structures.

Fig.4. Relationship between contact angle and halogen content (wt%) of modified rubbers (at 20°C)

Fig.5. Tape test using iron strips

Fig.6. Tape test using aluminium strips

(A) Halogen additional rubbers
 (B) Dihalocarbene modified rubbers
 •---Shown in 2-3-2)

3-3) Relation between the C-X dipolemoment in molecule and the polarity of polymer.

It is usual that the carbon-halogen atoms (C-X) dipolemoment in halogenated rubber is the main factor to govern the polarity of the whole polymer.

For discussing the polarity of polymer, therefore, we must estimate the C-X dipolemoment in dihalocarbene modified rubber compared with halogen additional rubber.

Considering two C-X bonds in dihalocarbene modified rubber, the interaction between both C-X bonds is quite strong due to their α -dihalo structure, since two C-X bonds in α -dihalo structure are fixed each other with the angle of about 110° as shown in Fig.7. Therefore the total dipolemoment of two C-X bonds in the direction perpendicular to the main C-C chain will be 1.14 times larger than one C-X dipolemoment, which is 57% in magnitude comparing with the case that two C-X bonds stand perpendicular to the main C-C chain.

In the case of halogen additional rubbers, on the other hand, the interaction between both C-X bonds is not strong due to their β -dihalo structure, shown in Fig.7, where two C-X bonds rotate almost freely around the main C-C chain, although there exist three points of the minimum free energy. Then, the total dipolemoment of two C-X bonds in the direction perpendicular to the main C-C chain will be 1.88 times larger comparing with one C-X dipolemoment.

Fig.7. C-X dipolemoment in the chemical structure

In consequence of this, the dipolemoment coming from two C-X bonds in the direction perpendicular to the main C-C chain for dihalocarbene modified rubber is only 60% comparing with that for halogen additional rubber, in spite of the higher polarity in the former than that in the latter as mentioned before. This result is contrary to our commonsense expectation that the higher the dipolemoment, the higher the polarity, which leads us to consider both halogenated rubbers from the viewpoint of higher order structure in polymer.

3-4) Polarity and higher order structure

DSC curve for 1.2 polybutadiene in Fig.8 showed the existence of the glass transition temperature (T_g) and the endothermic peak corresponding to the melting of crystal.

By modification with dihalocarbene, however, T_g in 1.2 polybutadiene shifted to higher temperature and the endothermic peak disappeared. This means that the crystallization of 1.2 polybutadiene was prevented by the introduction of rigid and bulky dihalocarbene, which made 1.2 polybutadiene amorphous state.

On the other hand, T_g and the crystallization of 1.2 polybutadiene was scarcely affected by the modification with halogen shown in Fig.8, which indicates the crystal in 1.2 polybutadiene was still remained as it was even after the modification. That is, mobility of each molecule in halogen modified rubber is restricted, because crystals in the system play a role in fixing molecules,

just like crosslinking.

Fig.8. Change of DSC Chart by modifications

- (A) Halogen addition
- (B) Dihalocarbene modification
- Halogen content (wt%)

Consequently, each molecule in dihalocarbene modified rubber can move freely because of its amorphous state, and the C-X bonds in dihalocarbene modified rubber can easily orientate to the direction perpendicular to the interface with metal. Whereas, in halogen additional rubber, the orientation of the C-X bonds is restricted significantly, the situations being shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9. Difference of high order structure between halogen additional rubber and dihalocarbene modified rubber

These results seems to produce the phenomena that the polarity of dihalocarbene modified rubber is higher than that of halogen additional rubber, despite of higher polarity in molecule for the latter than for the former as described before.

Going a step further, therefore, we performed an experiment to make sure our speculation that the polarity of polymer which have the high dipolemoment as a molecule itself will be lower if there are obstacles to prevent molecular movement. Fig.10 shows the change of the contact angle for dihalocarbene modified rubber (30% brominated) with addition of dicumyl peroxide (DCPO). As would be expected, the contact angle increases, then the polarity decreases with

increasing DCPO content. Naturally, the peeling strength lowered significantly from 15.0 kg/cm (DCPO not added) to 3.0 kg/cm (DCPO=2phr)

These results clearly indicate the correctness of our suppeculation that the high bond strength of dihalocarbene modified rubber as adhesive strongly depends on its higher order structure.

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Fig10. Effect of crosslinking on contact angle (at 24°C)